

Synthetic and structural studies of a novel nitrogen containing dinucleating macrocycle

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N-Bonded octahedral complexes of a new 20-membered dinucleating anionic macrocyclic ligand 8,9,10 : 18,19,20-pyo₂-3,4,5 : 13,14,15-(4-methylphenoxy)₂-[20]-1,3,6,8,11,13,16,18-octaenato[2-]-1,7,9,11,17,19-N₆ or pyo₂[20]octaenato[2-]N₆ have been prepared by condensation of 2,6-diformyl-4-methylphenol (DFMP) with 2,6-diaminopyridine (DAP) in presence of metal salts (M = Co^{II} and Ni^{II}) in 1 : 1 : 1 ratio.

In this paper we report the preparation and characterization of a new 20-membered, N-containing anionic macrocyclic ligand pyo₂[20]octaenato[2-]N₆ and its Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes. The macrocyclic complexes are prepared by *in situ* condensation of the two ligand moieties and the metal salts.

Results and discussion

The coloured complexes have high melting points. They are soluble in DMSO and DMF and slightly soluble in common polar organic solvents. Molar conductance values of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes are 230 and 235 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹, respectively.

IR spectra of the dialdehyde (DFMP) reveal bands at 1690 (C=O aromatic aldehyde group)¹, 3525 (phenolic), 2885 (C-H of aldehyde) and 3000 cm⁻¹ (C-H aromatic ring). The metal complexes show a new band at 1645–1640 cm⁻¹ (C=N- group)² shifted to lower region, indicating coordination through azomethine-N. The absence of band due to phenolic group, indicates bonding of OH group to the metal ion through its deprotonation. The coordination through nitrogen and oxygen atoms is confirmed by the occurrence of new bands at 485–465 and 550–500 cm⁻¹, respectively³. The presence of uncoordinated acetate ions is indicated by the peaks at 1595–1590 and 1355–1350 cm⁻¹ corresponding to asymmetric and symmetric vibrations, respectively. The bands due to pyridine ring are observed at 610–600 (in-plane) and 400–395 cm⁻¹ (out-of-plane). ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) of the dicarbaldehyde (DFMP) reveal signals at δ 2.4 (3H, s, Me), 7.8 (2H, s, ArH), 10.2 (2H, s, aldehydic) and 11.4 (1H, s, phenolic). The complexes reveal new signals at δ 3.3 (6H, m, -CH₃COO⁻)⁴, 5.1–5.2 (4H, s, H₂O), 7.6–7.9 (6H, m, pyridine-H) and 8.3–8.4 (4H, s, azomethine-H)⁵ showing

the condensation of DFMP with DAP, which is also indicated by disappearance of the signals of protons of aldehyde group. Deprotonation of phenolic-OH is also confirmed by the absence of signal of OH group in the complexes. The UV spectral bands at 8500, 16050 and 20390 cm⁻¹ correspond to ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}, ⁴A_{2g} and ⁴T_{1g} (P), respectively, indicating octahedral geometry⁶ around the central Co-atoms, which is also supported by its effective magnetic moment value of 4.45 B.M.⁷ The Ni-complex shows bands at 10850, 16510 and 26900 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}, ³T_{1g} and ³T_{1g} (P), respectively, suggesting octahedral geometry⁸ which is also confirmed by its effective magnetic moment value of 1.98 B.M. This value is less than normal probably due to antiferromagnetic interaction between the two Ni-atoms⁹.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The solvents were distilled and purified prior to use. 2,6-Diformyl-4-methylphenol (DFMP) was prepared according to reported method¹⁰, (yield, 28%), yellow, m.p. 130°.

Co^{II} and Ni^{II} dinuclear macrocyclic complexes. General procedure : To 2,6-diaminopyridine (1 mmol) in methanol (10 ml), the metal salt [0.25 g of (CH₃COO)₂Co.4H₂O/0.24 g of (CH₃COO)₂Ni.4H₂O] dissolved in water (10 ml) was added and the resulting mixture was refluxed with stirring for 30 min. DFMP (1 mmol) dissolved in methanol (10 ml) was then added to it and refluxed with stirring for 3–4 h. On cooling, the resulting precipitate was washed with cold water and methanol followed by ether. The complexes were dried over anhyd. CaCl₂ in a vacuum desiccator under reduced pressure : Co₂(C₃₂H₃₀N₆O₈) (32%), black, m.p. 300°; Ni₂(C₃₂H₃₀N₆O₈) (38%), brown, m.p. 310°. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

C, H and N were analyzed on a Carlo-Erba 1106 analyzer. Co and Ni were estimated by standard methods. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Jasco-Report-100 spectrophotometer, ^1H NMR spectra (CDCl_3) on a Bruker AC (300 MHz) spectrometer and UV spectra (DMSO) on a Shimadzu UV 150-150.02 spectrophotometer. Conductance was measured (in 10^{-3} M solutions of complexes in DMSO) using a Toshniwal CLO.1.10A conductivity bridge and magnetic susceptibility at room temperature by Gouy's method.

References

1. F. Mathis, *Bull. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **9D**, 22.
2. S. M. Pang, G. C. Gordon and V. L. Goedkar, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, **17**, 119.
3. J. E. Koracie, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1967, **23**, 183.
4. L. Spanel and M. A. Anderson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **113**, 2826.
5. M. Shakir, S. P. Varkey and D. Kumar, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1994, **13**, 941.
6. H. B. Pancholi and M. M. Patel, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 86.
7. L. Y. Martin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 2968.
8. A. K. Panda, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **71**, 89.
9. L. Sacconi, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1972, **8**, 35.
10. R. R. Gagne, C. L. Spiro, T. J. Smith, C. A. Hainnan, W. R. Thies and A. K. Shiemke, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 4073.